

This dataset was prepared for the participants in the second championship phase of the Open Challenge organized by the CHAIMELEON project for the training of AI models to resolve a specific clinical question related to Colon cancer:

predict patient's TNM.

All 679 colon cases (images and clinical data) collected until November 2023 were initially taken. Then 47 cases were excluded due to missing TNM information, 3 due to T0 cases and other 61 cases due to missing baseline CT.

From the 568 resulting cases, 408 were selected for the training partition and so included in this dataset:

- **64 T1/T2, 218 T3, 78 T4a, 23 T4b**
- **255 N0, 94 N1, 54 N2**
- **364 M0, 39 M1**

All the original series (DICOM) collected are included.

Only images from diagnosis.

In the Open Challenge only demographic and diagnosis information (excl. clinical TNM and biopsy-related information) was shared with the participants, but here the complete clinical data is included in the eforms.json file.

The ground truth for the clinical question in that case (TNM) is in those variables:

- tumor_pathology_category (T)
- regional_nodes_pathological_category (N)
- metastasis_pathological_category (M)

ID: f90ab277-9f66-448e-a996-f55a7866580b

URL: <https://chameleon-eu.i3m.upv.es/dataset-service/datasets/f90ab277-9f66-448e-a996-f55a7866580b/details>

Creation date: 2024-04-23 10:30:14.241152+00:00

License: CHAIMELEON Consortium 1.0 [<https://chameleon-eu.i3m.upv.es/dataset-service/web/terms-and-conditions.pdf>]

Contact info.: <https://chameleon.eu/#contact>

Studies count: 408

Subjects count: 408

Age range: Between 40 years and 94 years

Sex: Male, Female

Body part(s): ABDOMEN, CHEST, BRAIN, NECK, LUNG, WHOLEBODY, EXTREMITY, AORTA, TORAX, CAP, Unknown

Modality: CT